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THE ADVANCEMENT OF CULTURAL APPROACH TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN RUSSIA AT THE EDGE OF THE XX – XXIst CENTURY

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Abstract. At the end of the XX – beginning of the XXI century after the fall of the "Iron Curtain", the rapid development of international cooperation with the countries of the world in the political, economic, social and cultural spheres actualized the knowledge of foreign languages. The education system was tasked with finding new ways of learning and new ways of organizational forms of education that could prepare students for subsequent intercultural communication. There was an opinion that the culturological approach has a qualitative potential for transforming foreign language teaching, and its sub-species will help solve some key issues on preparing future graduates for life in harmony with representatives of other cultures and peoples. In this article, the authors analyze the culturological approach to teaching a foreign language and show the history of its development at the turn of the XX – XXI century. The role of linguistic, cross-cultural approach, intercultural, socio-cultural and multicultural approaches as invariants of the cultural approach is emphasized. The authors analyze the scientific works of Russian researchers, methodologists and teachers who focus on the development and significance of the cultural approach in the framework of the study of the discipline "Foreign language". The importance of the formation of intercultural competence, knowledge and understanding of another culture as a strategic task of teaching a foreign language in higher education within the framework of a culturological approach is emphasized.

Keywords: culturological approach, foreign language, teacher, intercultural competence, intercultural communication, culture

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РАЗВИТИЕ КУЛЬТУРОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА К ПРЕПОДАВАНИЮ ИНОСТРАННОГО ЯЗЫКА В ОТЕЧЕСТВЕННОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ НА РУБЕЖЕ XX – XXI в.

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Аннотация. В конце XX – начале XXI в. после падения «железного занавеса» стремительное развитие международного взаимодействия со странами мира в политической, экономической, социальной и культурной сферах актуализировали владение иностранными языками. Перед системой образования была поставлена задача поиска новых способов обучения и новых организационных форм образования, которые могли бы подготовить обучающихся к последующей межкультурной коммуникации. Существовало мнение, что качественным потенциалом для преобразования обучения иностранному языку обладает культурологический подход, а его реализация поможет решить некоторые ключевые вопросы подготовки выпускников высшей школы к жизни в гармонии с представителями других культур. В данной статье авторы изучают культурологический подход к преподаванию иностранного языка и показывают историю его развития на рубеже XX – XXI в. Подчеркивается роль лингвострановедческого, страноведческого, межкультурного, социокультурного и поликультурного подхода как инвариантов культурологического подхода. Авторы анализируют научные работы отечественных исследователей, методистов и педагогов, которые центрируются на разработке и значимости культурологического подхода в рамках изучения дисциплины «Иностранный язык». Особо отмечается важность формирования межкультурной компетенции, знания и понимания иной культуры как стратегической задачи преподавания иностранного языка в высшей школе в рамках культурологического подхода.

Ключевые слова: культурологический подход, иностранный язык, межкультурная компетенция, межкультурная коммуникация, культура

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During the 1990s and the early 2000s, scholars specializing in the discipline of foreign language studies developed methodologies aimed at integrating cultural knowledge into the learning process. The pedagogical community also rethought, supplemented and expanded the already existing approaches to teaching a foreign language that appeared in earlier periods.

The interest in the culturological approach during this period stemmed from the imperative of shaping a "cultured individual," which was a key objective for the education system. This approach aimed to tackle the challenges associated with nurturing an individual's cultural refinement and readiness for the swiftly evolving landscape of international cooperation, when after the fall of the "Iron Curtain" Russia rapidly integrated into the world political, economic and cultural space.

Therefore, Russian teachers and methodologists turned to different perspectives of its consideration, including issues of its implementation in teaching a foreign language. As a result, a fairly large number of works have appeared devoted to the study of the cultural approach and its variants, for example: "Socio-cultural approach to teaching a foreign language as a specialty" [14] ("Sociokul'turnyj podhod k obucheniyu inostrannomu yazyku kak special'nosti") (V. V. Safonova 1992), "Poetry in a foreign language lesson: modern approaches to teaching reading" [8] (T. P. Kamaeva, L. V. Karpova, I. M. Deeva 1996), "Linguo-foreign studies approach in teaching French in the lower grades" [9] ("Lingvostrannovedcheskij podhod pri obuchenii francuzskomu yazyku v mladshih klassah") (S. M. Kashchuk 1997), "Intercultural communication and teaching German" [6] ("Mezhkul'turnaya kommunikaciya i prepodavanie nemeckogo yazyka") (V. P. Furmanova 2002) and others.

The paper explores the significance of adopting a culturological approach in teaching foreign language, emphasizing its role as a vital component of educational content and as a determining factor in the use of language within specific cross-cultural dialogue situations. First of all, the approaches that are focused on the study of the culture of other peoples.

At the close of the 1990s and the start of the XXIst century considerable attention is beginning to be

paid to the use of language in certain socio-cultural situations. It is during this period that there is an awareness of the need to teach students cultural information about the countries in which the studied language is spoken. Understanding the mentality and lifestyle of different cultures is crucial for effective intercultural communication, whether in personal or professional spheres. It facilitates meaningful connections and collaboration, which are essential in our increasingly interconnected world. Traditional approaches that focused on individual points (whether grammar or vocabulary memorization) were unable to prepare students for real, spontaneous communication with a native speaker. The social and cultural rules that exist in real life are decisive factors in communication. The function of culture is the correct choice of the register of utterance, depending on the role and purpose of communication. Cultural awareness is essential for accurately interpreting specific situations in foreign cultural environments. Familiarity with a culture can help overcome communication barriers, allowing individuals from diverse cultures, despite their differences, to depend on cultural knowledge. That is why knowledge about the culture of other peoples helps in intercultural communication, and they certainly should be formed in students.

During this period I. M. Deeva, N.D. Galskova, T. P. Kamaeva, L. V. Karpova, S. M. Kashchuk, V.S. Krasilnikova, A. G. Krupko, E.I. Passov, N.A. Salanovich, V. V. Safonova, P. V. Sysoev, E. G. Tareva, T.N. Chaynikova, G.M. Chernova, V. P. Furmanova and other scientists-educators made an important contribution to the development of various approaches based on culturological information about the country of the studied language.

The interest of scientists has contributed to the fact that today in the arsenal of teachers there are linguistic-cultural, linguo-cultural (linguoculturological), cross-cultural approach, literary and cross-cultural approach, socio-cultural, intercultural, multicultural and other approaches. Despite the seemingly different names, they are all united by one idea. The central focus of foreign language instruction should include: vocabulary, grammar, and phonetics. It also includes the culture of the country connected to the language under study. Understanding the cultural aspects is essential

for a comprehensive and meaningful language learning experience. As a rule, in science these approaches are called culturological or cultural studies. To clarify their common and different features, we will focus on the characteristics of some of them as they arise and develop.

Linguistic-cultural approach. A. G. Krupko believes that linguistics is a cognitive value and contributes to the realization of a general educational goal in a foreign language lesson. The linguistic-cultural approach promotes familiarity with the country of the studied language, with its traditions, people and broadens the students' general horizons. The author notes that the perception of foreign culture always occurs through the prism of one's own. Therefore, the linguistic-cultural approach facilitates the development of cross-cultural competence, enriching students' analytical abilities in comparing foreign cultures with their own [11].

Knowledge of the country's culture contributes to a more accurate and deep understanding of the language. The linguistic-cultural approach increases interest and motivation to learn a language. A large amount of authentic illustrative material is used in the classroom, teachers take into account the realities that students may encounter in communicating with native speakers. Classes pay attention to role-playing games and discussions, while written and oral exercises of a problem-searching nature are practiced.

A. G. Krupko observes that genuine visual exposure provides a more effective understanding of the culture and, to some extent, assists students in grasping concepts that may be lacking in their own culture, thus offering a comprehensive comprehension of foreign realities [11].

V.S. Krasilnikova and T.S. Chaynikova characterize the contemporary phase of foreign language instruction as prioritizing the educational and developmental dimensions of the instructional content. They contend that adopting a linguistic-cultural approach in the curation and structuring of educational materials contributes to the effective absorption of the historical and cultural nuances of the target language's associated country. The authors also assert that using a linguo-cultural approach aims to integrate elements of foreign language culture, enhance cognitive activity, and create positive motivation [10].

S. M. Kashchuk asserts that the linguo-cultural approach entails acquainting students with a new culture through the medium of language during the learning process. In the classroom, there is an acquaintance with the new reality, with the customs and traditions of the people [9].

We see that the interest in the linguistic-cultural approach is caused by the need to co-study the language and culture, which contributes to productive communication in a real-life situation, when meeting a representative of another culture, it's crucial to have not only linguistic skills but also knowledge about the interlocutor's culture.

Beginning of the XXI century, the economic and cultural situation of modern society obliges people to be able to coexist in the new world. Language acts as a vital tool for nurturing mutual understanding and interaction among individuals of varying faiths. Aiming to foster a mutually beneficial dialogue and cultivate humanitarian intercultural connections among representatives. The notion put forth by N. D. Galskova, which delves into the challenge of nurturing individuals' capacity for intercultural communication, presents an intriguing concept. She writes: "The subject of intercultural communication simultaneously tries to take into account not only a different language code, but also other customs and habits, other norms of social behavior" [3].

The requirements of intercultural communication are a rethinking of the essence and content of learning goals. N. D. Galskova calls two approaches interrelated and mutually dependent on each other in teaching culture and foreign languages. The *linguo-ethnoecological* approach highlights the importance and essential nature of studying one's native language and culture. Understanding one's linguistic and cultural roots is crucial for personal and communal identity, as well as understanding one's connection to a particular ethnic group and multicultural community. The *interlinguocultural* approach focuses on the development of foreign cultures and civilizations, the study of traditions. The author concludes that employing these two approaches in foreign language education will enhance an individual's social mobility within the labor market. That will also allow them to develop in professional activity.

In this regard, N.D. Galskova believes that the intercultural aspect of the educational process should strive to seek psychological, pedagogical, and methodological solutions. These solutions will shape the foreign language teaching system in a manner that allows students to gain personalized experience in communicating with another linguistic culture [3].

E. A. Lavrinenko mentions the linguistic-culture approach in his work, believing that having originated in the 1970s, he did not lose his importance and position among other equally important approaches in the study of a foreign language at the turn of the XX-XXI centuries. According to the author's perspective, the significance of the linguistic and cultural approach lies in the extraction of national and cultural information for application in diverse communication scenarios. The author aptly asserts that studies in linguocultural encompass language phenomena that mirror culture as a whole.

The linguistic-cultural approach holds considerable importance in addressing crucial socio-cultural issues like: the acculturation of personality. However, E. A. Lavrinenko does not deny the importance of a communicative and grammatical approach to teaching foreign languages, but on the contrary, combining with them, the linguistic-cultural approach is filled with a new goal – "achieving an adequate existence of a linguistic personality in a new linguistic and cultural world" [12].

In our opinion, the presented statements actualize the requirements of teaching perception and understanding of a different linguistic picture of the world's fragment.

Another approach that focuses on the study of the studied culture is the cross-cultural approach. *Cross-cultural studies* – knowledge about the country – contributes to the enrichment of national cultures and helps to study national values, which are an integral part of universal values. The volume of background knowledge is expanding, thereby ensuring successful communication in the language. It is also important to note that cross-cultural studies also perform an educational function, fostering respect and love for the country of the studied language.

G.M. Chernova highlights the fundamental principle of the cross-cultural approach in foreign lan-

guage education as fostering high motivation for active, conscious, and creative student engagement in the learning of both the language and the associated culture. In her opinion, the proposed approach will stimulate cognitive interest and meet the educational needs of students [4].

Obviously, the interest in learning a language is based on an interest in the culture of the country. The cultural dimension of teaching a foreign language forms not just conceptual knowledge, but also binds them to certain elements of the system of a foreign language and foreign language speech.

Literary and cross-cultural approach. In 1996, the work of the team of authors T. P. Kamaeva, L. V. Karpova and I. M. Deeva appeared on the topic "Poetry in a foreign language lesson: modern approaches to teaching reading" [8] ("Poe`ziya na uroke inostrannogo yazy`ka: sovremenny`e podxody` k obucheniyu chteniyu"). The authors refer to "poetry" as a contemporary method for instructing reading in a foreign language lesson. They propose using genuine problem-based material for discussion to foster the personal development of students, which in turn positively impacts motivation and promotes diverse forms of interaction in the classroom. Thus, the poetic work presents potential opportunities for engaging students in collaborative, subject-focused, and motivated communicative activities among themselves and with the teacher.

The literary and cross-cultural approach is a factor of developing learning, which expands the horizons of students, and also forms a cross-cultural competence. The authors also note that the use of samples of foreign language poetry can be one of the effective means of achieving the practical, educational and developmental goals of teaching the subject [8].

It is obvious that linguoculturology is beginning to attract the attention of an increasing number of scientists and methodologists in Russia. "A person's belonging to a certain culture determines the world of their language" [17]. Language is quite an important component of culture and enables a deeper understanding of the system of values and cultural characteristics of the people. The knowledge gained in foreign language classes using a culturological approach

is not the end result of training, but represents the basis for further development of creative and professional potential.

Socio-cultural approach. In the early 90s there has been a consistent trend in language pedagogy towards integrating cognitive, developmental, value-oriented, and communicative-practical aspects of foreign language education as an academic discipline. As a result, the groundwork for intercultural interaction in a multicultural world is gradually being established. Cultural sociologization of foreign language education is becoming a socio-pedagogical direction and is characterized by a didactic combination of language and culture teaching for rapidly expanding intercultural and cross-cultural communication. There is an enrichment of the cultural picture of the world of students, when the study of ethnic, national, regional and continental cultures contributes not only to the comprehension of native culture, but also to the understanding that cultural diversity is an immutable fact that should certainly be considered in real communication.

Representing one of the strategic paradigms in contemporary language education V. V. Safonova thinks that the socio-cultural approach is indeed a significant direction for the integrated study of language and culture. This approach is aimed at teaching intercultural foreign language communication for the purposes of civil peace and harmony. The author's belief is that the socio-cultural approach takes precedence due to its socio-pedagogical orientation towards teaching a foreign language within the framework of a cultural exchange. The socio-cultural approach is aimed at revealing the personality-forming potential of a foreign language as a means of educating a humanistic personality [14].

The emergence and development of socio-cultural, linguo-regional, linguo-ethnoecological, interlinguocultural, and cross-cultural approaches in the early 1990s were responses to the mandate placed upon the national education system to cultivate individuals who:

- 1) are prepared to collaborate in the spirit of peace and intercultural dialogue;
- 2) recognize the role of their profession in the advancement of their country, the global community, and international cooperation;
- 3) are eager to actively contribute to the fortification and progress of peace.

An intercultural approach is also aimed at the implementation of this task. The cultural aspect of education demands novel psychological, pedagogical, and methodological approaches geared towards fostering communicative and intercultural competence, while also broadening the scope of the educational process. An intercultural approach is aimed at achieving this goal. Modern scientists and educators believe that the intercultural approach is a broader methodological direction in contrast to the linguo-cultural, linguo-cultural or socio-cultural, because it represents a common paradigm of teaching a foreign language.

Multiple definitions of the intercultural approach exist, all of which underscore the significance of learning about diverse cultures, worldview and cultural characteristics of native speakers. A. S. Budnik believes that cross-cultural studies, linguoculturological and socio-cultural knowledge are necessary for students to successfully communicate. The main criterion of the intercultural approach is understanding the relationship between "one's own" and "someone else's," recognizing that they are not inherently hostile categories.

The author believes that the intercultural approach represents the idea of the equal presence of two cultures. An important point is to take into account the personal aspect, which includes awareness, empathy and reflection. Given the inextricable link between language and culture. The intercultural approach relies on students' ability to apply their knowledge to interpret foreign language culture and compare it with their own. An integral aspect of promoting intercultural dialogue is establishing a balanced relationship between the two cultures. It's crucial to gain cross-cultural, linguistic-cultural, and socio-cultural knowledge when learning a foreign language, and to reevaluate one's perspective of the role of native culture in a global context, recognizing its contribution to world culture.

A.S. Budnik reminds that at the senior stage of education, the intercultural approach is particularly relevant. "The goal is to enable students to compare their native culture with the foreign language culture. Intercultural knowledge is developed in a way that motivates students to actively engage in the dialogue of cultures" [2].

In the context of studying intercultural communication and foreign language education, V. P.

Furmanova suggests that culture plays a dual role as both an activity and a process of self-evolution. Each culture harbors its own norms of perception and cognition, which are comprehended through comparison within a particular semantic framework. The author posits that through intercultural communication, a communicative space emerges, portraying culture as a system and a mode of operation. Language, in turn, functions as a tool and manifestation of cultural conduct [6].

N. A. Kaftailova also believes that the intercultural approach is at the heart of the modernization of the linguistic education system. Recently, many new terms with intercultural content have appeared in linguodidactics, for example: "intercultural education, intercultural communication, intercultural education, intercultural learning, intercultural competence, intercultural competency, intercultural approach" [11]. According to the teacher, "the intercultural approach is preparing students for the effective implementation of intercultural communication in the process of learning a language" [11]. Intercultural communication and mutual understanding between participants are built according to the rules adopted in the particular culture. Additionally, intercultural communication is guided by its own distinctive features and characteristics.

G. V. Zakharova also considers an intercultural approach to teaching foreign languages. The intercultural approach is a direct connection with someone else's socio-cultural reality, which subsequently affects its perception. When communicating with speakers of a different culture, the student needs to show his own culture and a specific point of view, he needs to take part in something alien to him. Thus, a space is created for a new look [18].

The author suggests using foreign literature while teaching foreign languages, because literary texts reveal some special advantages. In relation to the world, literary texts are more open and help to manifest the inner world of a person. Embracing the intercultural approach in foreign language education indeed allows students to compare elements of their own culture with the culture associated with the language being studied. This plays a pivotal role in fos-

tering both intercultural and socio-cultural competence, empowering students to make independent decisions within the realm of culture [18].

Therefore, we understand that the intercultural approach makes it possible to better understand the foreign language culture, the mentality of the country in another cultural society. New forms of social relations in the conditions of economic transformations in Russia in the late 90s were aimed at reforming all aspects of social life, including the education system. This meant the revision of educational programs in accordance with the world standard. The education system was faced with the task of preparing future specialists for professional and personal interacting with individuals from diverse cultures.

Multicultural approach.

Researchers ascribe varied conceptual content to the terms "multicultural education" and "multicultural approach." It merits significant attention. A. S. Dunaeva underscores that the bedrock of multicultural education is rooted in the principle of multiculturalism, a humanistic notion that rejects the inherent superiority or inferiority of any culture. Each culture possesses distinct strengths and weaknesses, thereby challenging the education system to convert cultural diversity into a pursuit of value-based principles. The development of students' attitudes toward other cultures is of utmost importance, as it ensures the freedom of cultural self-identification and facilitates self-realization within the diversity of modern culture [5].

The multicultural approach was developed according to the methodology of multicultural education, which recognizes the presence of a multitude of equivalent cultures. E. A. Isaev considers this approach as "realizing the conjugation of several cultural traditions in goals, content, methods and organizational forms and leading to the assimilation by the subjects of education of the phenomena of cultural diversity as a social norm and personal value, and images of culture and personality – as a result of creative intercultural interaction" [7].

The fundamental position of multicultural education and multicultural approach were implemented in the Concept of Linguistic Multicultural Education developed in 2008 by P.V. Sysoev. The author acknowledges that V.V. Safonova developed their concept

which is notably influenced by the socio-cultural approach to selecting educational material. He believes that "linguistic multicultural education is a process of mastering knowledge about the cultural diversity of the surrounding world of the countries of co-studied languages and about the relationship between cultures in the modern multicultural world, as well as the formation of an active life position and skills to interact with representatives of different countries and cultures according to the principle of dialogue of cultures" [15].

P. V. Sysoev holds the viewpoint that the multicultural approach to language teaching is one of the dominant methods, reflecting the unique nature of simultaneously teaching a foreign language and culture. This approach involves utilizing culturally diverse thematic materials including ethnic, social, religious, professional, and geographical aspects. Accordingly, through the study of a foreign language, individuals are taught, developed, and educated [16].

We can conclude that the goal of the multicultural approach is to cultivate a linguistic personality capable of multicultural self-organization and development within the cross-cultural sphere. Students come to understand cultural diversity as a standard aspect of coexistence among cultures in contemporary multicultural societies within the countries where their native and studied languages are spoken [7]. Consequently, the main goal of the multicultural approach to foreign language instruction is the formed multiculturalism of the individual, i.e. the individual who knows not only his native culture, but also other cultures.

Based on the analysis, the following tasks were assigned to the subject "Foreign language" in this period encompasses:

- 1) the practical mastery of basic speech skills;

- 2) the expansion of horizons and enrichment of knowledge about literature, art, geography, history, life, and traditions of different countries;

- 3) fostering respect for other peoples.

Of course, changes in the content of teaching foreign languages could not but affect the number of hours allocated to their study, as well as to increase their diversity. As E.A. Braslavskaya notes: "The language policy of this time period is characterized by the following innovations: 1) the number of hours spent learning foreign languages has increased; 2) the number of languages studied has increased" [1].

Thus, the 90s of the XX - the first decade of the XXI century became a turning point in rethinking the content of the process of teaching foreign languages, the development of methodology, because people had an urgent need to learn languages in order to communicate with representatives of other countries. The cultural approach at the turn of the XX – XXI centuries became strategically important, because its main task was to introduce students to other cultures for effective interaction with them.

The culturological approach and its invariants – sociocultural, linguo-cultural, linguo-ethnoecological, interlinguocultural, cross-cultural, intercultural, multicultural - are based on the idea of an indispensable co-study of language and culture, which in modern works is interpreted as the culturological idea of teaching a foreign language. The culturological approach focuses not only on language skills, but also on the cultural component, revealing to students with cultural heritage and societal norms of the people from the country where the language is spoken. The fulfilment of the culturological approach is aimed at a deeper understanding of another culture, which in turn should contribute to effective intercultural communication.

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